

Analysis of wave impacts on vertical walls along the Saint-Lawrence gulf using a FANS model

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Abstract

Climate change and the associated rise in sea levels impose a challenge for current methods used to predict the processes involved in wave-coastal structure interactions. The main objective of this study is to extend the range of numerical tools available to coastal engineers by presenting a compressible turbulence model to study wave dynamic interactions with impermeable structures. A solver is developed in *OpenFOAM*[®] by using the adiabatic equation of state coupled with the $k - \omega$ SST turbulence model and the Volume of Fluid (VOF) interface capture method. The model is first validated with two experimental test cases: a sloshing tank with impacts, and wave impacts on a vertical wall with an overhanging slab. After validation, the model is confidently used for the analysis of wave interactions with vertical walls along the Saint-Lawrence gulf. Four incident wave cases representing frequent and extreme storm conditions are selected using the statistical data of a buoy located *in situ*. Results are discussed primarily in terms of the loads and overtopping on the structure for two breaking and two non-breaking wave cases.

Keywords: Wave impact, impermeable structures, overtopping, FANS model

1. Introduction

In the upcoming years, global warming will intensify and sea level will continue to rise. As a consequence of this, greater and more frequent floods are to be expected, along with damage to properties and structures protecting the coastline. For instance, about 40% of the worldwide population is settled directly on the seashore [1] and most of these areas will be negatively affected by sea level rise. The high concentration of activities, services and population in coastal regions coupled with the effects of sea level rising pose a challenge for coastal protection, adaptation and mitigation alternatives, which requires proper quantification of the coastal structures as well as knowing and limiting their uncertainty in terms of design. These new demands ask for new methods to improve the design and quantification of the processes affecting such structures against more catastrophic scenarios.

The most commonly built coastal protection structures include breakwaters and vertical walls (or seawalls). While the former mainly dissipates wave energy by wave breaking on the structure, seawalls are normally designed to produce wave reflection. Hence, these coastal reflecting structures

are usually built to protect against strong and violent wave impacts in coastal areas close to beaches and with intense human activity. Fluid loading on these structures can be evaluated if the spatial and temporal wave-structure interactions that include wave pressures and wave-breaking are known. Several decades ago, the incident wave interactions with a seawall have been studied by performing experimental tests in laboratory and developing mechanical models. Bagnold [2], De Rouville [3] and Denny [4] laid out most of the pioneering works on the behaviour and design of seawalls. Experimental studies have shown that the resulting loads on the structure are largely dependent on the wave shape and breaker type at the wall. The wave-breaking on a structure is influenced by many parameters including (i) the structure characteristics (e.g., geometry, construction materials), (ii) the water depth in front of the structure, h , (iii) the incident sea state that is characterized by the relative water depth, h/L , and the wave steepness, H/L , (being L the wavelength and H the wave height), and (iv) the topography in front of the structure [5]. In general, past experimental results have highlighted a great variability due to the number of parameters involved and the intrinsic uncertainty of testing. Moreover, field and laboratory experiments are also limited by their significant costs and scaling issues [6]. The latter is a crucial point in the study of wave impacts against vertical structures since air compressibility plays a major role in the resulting pressure distribution and forces on the wall [7].

In this context, numerical models based on the Reynolds- (RANS) or Favre-Averaged Navier-Stokes (FANS) equations represent valuable tools to quantify and measure processes and interactions with coastal structures. These models provide great detail regarding the hydrodynamics of interactions between incident waves, seabed and structures. Their popularity in this field has increased in recent years due to the wider access to high performance computers and the release of wave specific libraries such as *olaFlow* [8, 9] or *waves2foam* [10], which can be integrated within the *OpenFOAM*[®] framework. For instance, Castellino et al. [11] used an incompressible solver with the $k - \epsilon$ turbulence model to predict impulsive forces on recurved parapets under non-breaking waves. Buccino et al. [12] considered a similar approach to study overtopping and pressures around top caisson breakwaters. Other recent applications include the performance analysis of wave energy converters [13] and wave induced pressures against vertical walls [14] and vertical walls with overhanging slabs [15]. However, RANS models of wave impacts against impermeable structures often overlook air compressibility, though it plays a major role in plunging breakers and flip-through impacts, which usually generate the highest loads on the structure. Considering air as a compressible fluid adds density as another field variable, which is commonly dealt with by adding the ideal gas equation of state. However, this requires the solution of the energy equation, increasing thus the complexity and computational cost of the model. Since in wave dynamics, compressibility effects only manifest during certain breaker types, hybrid solvers combining incompressible (away from the structure) and compressible domains (close to the structure) have been developed [16]. A different approach was carried out by Gatin et al. [17], which presented a compressible solver for wave impacts using an adiabatic equation of state and the Ghost Fluid Method for capturing the water-air interface. The adiabatic equation of state allows to decouple the energy equation. The model showed good accuracy for modelling loadings against ship hulls and vertical walls.

Hence, the objective of this study is to extend the range of numerical tools available for coastal engineers, by presenting a compressible turbulence model to study full-scale the wave dynamic interactions with impermeable structures. To this end, a solver was developed in *OpenFOAM*[®] by using the adiabatic equation of state with the $k - \omega$ SST turbulence model and the Volume of Fluid (VOF) interface capture method. Waves are generated using the *olaFlow* library. Thus

we present a compressible turbulence model for wave-structure interactions readily available as an open-source code. After validation, the model is applied to study frequent events and extreme storms against a seawall located in the Saint-Lawrence gulf (Québec, Canada). The incident wave conditions were collected from statistical data provided by a buoy located in situ. To the best of the authors' knowledge, numerical studies of breaking wave impacts at real-life dimensions using a compressible solver are very scarce in the scientific literature.

The structure of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the numerical model implemented in *OpenFOAM*[®]. The validation of the model is shown in Section 3 using two experimental cases: (i) a sloshing tank with wave impacts, and (ii) wave impacts against a vertical structure with an overhanging slab. Section 4 analysis the results obtained from the application of this model to a coastal protection structure located in the Saint-Lawrence gulf (Québec, Canada). The paper ends with a summary of the most important conclusions that can be derived from this research in Section 5.

2. Numerical Setup

2.1. Governing equations

The flow is considered as a transient, Newtonian and turbulent pseudo-mixture of air (gas) and water (liquid), which is separated by a clear interface and shares velocity and pressure fields. Bredmose et al. [7] showed that air pressure and density variations play a central role during certain wave impacts. Thus, assuming the air is compressible and behaves as an adiabatic gas, the mean flow field is modelled using the Favre-Average Navier-Stokes (FANS) equations:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \mathbf{u}) + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} \rho \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p^* + \nabla \cdot (\mu_{eff} \nabla \mathbf{u}) + \sigma \kappa \nabla \alpha - \mathbf{g} \mathbf{x} \nabla \rho \quad (1b)$$

$$(1c)$$

where ρ and $\mathbf{u} = u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} + w\hat{k}$ are, respectively, the mean flow density and velocity, $p^* = p - \rho \mathbf{g} \mathbf{x}$ is the dynamic pressure, $\mathbf{g} = -9.81\hat{k} \text{ m s}^{-2}$ is the gravity vector, \mathbf{x} is the local position vector, μ_{eff} the effective dynamic viscosity, $\sigma = 0.07 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ the surface tension and $\kappa = \nabla \cdot \frac{\nabla \alpha}{|\nabla \alpha|}$ the interface curvature.

The location of each phase within the domain is determined using the Volume of Fluid method [18], which defines the water volume fraction α such that $\alpha = 1$ in fully submerged cells and $\alpha = 0$ in dry cells. The α field at each time step is computed using the Multidimensional Universal Limiter with Explicit Solution (MULES) algorithm which introduces the following modified transport equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \alpha + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \alpha + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}_c \alpha (1 - \alpha) = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $|\mathbf{U}_c| = \min [c_\alpha |\mathbf{u}|, \max(\mathbf{u})]$ and c_α is an interface compression parameter. The main advantage of this approach is its numerical stability and that it bounds $0 \geq \alpha \geq 1$, although it might be sensible to the grid orientation and requires a balanced scheme setup [19].

The mean flow density (ρ) and effective viscosity (μ_{eff}) are determined by mixing-type laws as:

$$\rho = \alpha \rho_w + (1 - \alpha) \rho_a, \quad (3)$$

$$\mu_{eff} = \alpha \mu_w + (1 - \alpha) \mu_a + \rho \nu_t \quad (4)$$

where ν_t is the turbulent/eddy kinematic viscosity. The subscripts a and w refer, respectively, to the air and water phases. In this study, ν_t is calculated using the the $k - \omega$ SST model [20]. Water density (ρ_w) is determined using a linear equation of state:

$$\rho_w = \rho_{0,w} + \Psi (p - p_0) \quad (5)$$

where $p_0 = 101.325$ kPa, $\rho_{0,w} = 998$ kg m⁻³ and $\Psi = (R_w T)^{-1}$ is the water compressibility factor ($R_w = 3$ kJ kg⁻¹ K⁻¹). Air density is computed using the adiabatic gas model:

$$\frac{p}{\rho_a^\gamma} = \frac{p_{ref}}{\rho_{ref}^\gamma} = const. \quad (6)$$

where $\gamma = 1.4$ is the air specific heat ratio and $p_{ref} = 1 \times 10^5$ Pa and $\rho_{ref} = 1$ kg m⁻³ are, respectively, the reference pressure and density. This model neglects heat transfer effects, which allows the energy and momentum equations to be decoupled. The model can be used in the context of wave impact dynamics since the events occur within a very short time frame and both phases tend to have the same temperature Gatin et al. [17]. Both the adiabatic gas model and the MULES algorithm were chosen via a numerical benchmark study where this combination performed better than other setups using the perfect gas model and/or the isoAdvector algorithm [21].

2.2. Numerical method

The model was implemented in *OpenFOAM*[®] v2006 using an in-house solver: *compressibleNoTInterFoam*. This is a modified version of the *compressibleInterFoam* solver, which does not include the energy equation. Table 1 summarizes the numerical parameters. Advection and diffusion terms are discretized using, respectively, upwind and central second-order schemes. The first-order Euler temporal scheme is employed for the temporal terms. Second-order and Crank-Nicholson temporal schemes were tried out in preliminary calculations but proved to be unstable or required excessively small time steps (1×10^{-12} s) without any noticeable improvement on the results. All cases were run on the Compute Canada clusters *Cedar* (WestGrid, www.westgrid.ca) and *Niagara* (SciNet [22, 23]), using between 40 and 120 nodes per case.

3. Model Validation

The model accuracy is assessed in this section by comparing the present results against two reference experimental test cases: (i) a sloshing tank [24] and (ii) regular wave impacts against a vertical wall [15]. The accuracy of the numerical setup is evaluated in terms of three statistical parameters as suggested by González-Cao et al. [15]. For this method, the model results and the (referential) experimental data are arranged in vectors \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , respectively. Both vectors have the same length N and their respective averages are $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{B}}$. The difference between \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} can

Parameter	Definition
Fluids	water-air
Water properties	liquid
Air properties	adiabatic gas
Turbulence model	$k - \omega$ SST
State	Transient
Temporal schemes	Euler (1 st order)
Diffusion scheme	Gauss linear (2 nd order)
Advection scheme	limitedLinear (2 nd order)
Solution algorithm	<i>PIMPLE</i>

Table 1. Summary of the fixed numerical parameters for all the configurations.

be quantified using two metrics: the *Accuracy index* (AI , Eq. (7)) and the *Skill index* (SI , Eq. (8)) defined as:

$$AI = |1 - R_A^2| + E_n \quad (7)$$

$$SI = \frac{4(1 + R_A)^4}{\left(\sigma_{n,A} + \frac{1}{\sigma_{n,A}}\right)^2 (1 + R_o)^4} \quad (8)$$

where R_A is the correlation coefficient between \bar{A} and \bar{B} , $R_o = 1$, E_n is the centred root-mean-square difference and σ_n is the normalized standard deviation. Notice that, according to Eqs. (7) and (8), $AI \rightarrow 0$ and $SI \rightarrow 1$ for a model that perfectly reproduces the experimental results.

3.1. Case 1: Sloshing tank with impact

This case considers a partially filled water tank with the dimensions shown in Fig. 1. The initial pressure is $p_o = 75\,000$ Pa and the initial water level is 0.125 m. The tank sway is described by the following equation:

$$x(t) = A_L \sin(\omega_L t) \quad (9)$$

with $A_L = 0.03$ m and $\omega_L = 3.926$ rad s⁻¹. Under these conditions, plunging impacts occur on both sides of the box.

The case was simulated using a structured mesh grid formed by dividing the domain in 500 elements along the x direction, 200 elements along the $z \leq 0.4$ m and 60 elements along $z > 0.4$ m. The Courant number was fixed to $Co = 0.1$, which lead to a varying time step between 10×10^{-8} s and 10×10^{-2} s. Pressure readings on the wall $x = 0$ (Fig. 1 generated by the numerical model are compared with the experimental data of Lugni et al. [24] and the numerical results of Ma et al. [25]. Ma et al. [25] used *compressibleInterFoam* in combination with the ideal gas law for the air properties and the MULES algorithm. The pressure sensors are located every 0.02 m between $z = 0.13$ m and 0.21 m. Fig. 2 shows the pressure reading at probes $p_{Lug,1}$ to $p_{Lug,4}$ for the third impact in the series, which generated the highest experimental pressure values. The experimental result shows a first pressure peak, followed by a series of decaying oscillations. These indicate the

Fig. 1. Sketch of the sloshing tank with impact.

presence of an air pocket compressing and expanding between the water front and the wall, which is a characteristic behaviour of plunging impacts. The present model properly captures this behaviour and shows a good approximation to the maximum pressure at each sensor. Moreover, the present model shows a better agreement with the pressure signals at sensors $P_{Lug,2}$ to $P_{Lug,4}$ (Figs. 2b- 2d) over the results of Ma et al. [25]. At sensor $P_{Lug,1}$ (Fig. 2a), the RANS model captures well the peak of the initial impact, but then predicts damping oscillations of larger amplitude and period. This difference might be attributed to the complexity of properly capturing the air-water interface since sensor $P_{Lug,1}$ is located closest to the SWL.

Table 2 summarizes the average statistics (over the five pressure sensors) for both the numerical RANS model and the numerical results of Ma et al. [25] using the experimental data as reference. For the present model, $R_A = 0.736$, $AI = 1.146$ which are slightly better than the corresponding values for the numerical results of Ma et al. [25] (respectively $R_A = 0.715$, $AI = 1.323$). Both approaches result in very similar SI values.

	E_N	$\sigma_{n,A}$	R_A	AI	SI
RANS Model <i>b</i>	0.688	0.811	0.736	1.146	0.543
Ma et al. [25]	0.835	1.034	0.715	1.323	0.540

Table 2. Comparison metrics for the present model and the numerical results of Ma et al. [25] using the experimental data of Lugni et al. [24] as reference. Case of a sloshing tank with impact.

Fig. 2. Temporal distributions of the relative pressure at points (a) $P_{Lug,1}$, (b) $P_{Lug,2}$, (c) $P_{Lug,3}$ and (d) $P_{Lug,4}$ (see points positions in Fig. 1. Comparison between the proposed model, the experimental data of Lugni et al. [24] and the numerical results of Ma et al. [25].

3.2. Case 2: Regular wave impacts against an impermeable wall

This case considers wave impacts against a vertical impermeable wall with a cantilever slab. It is based on the experimental and numerical results analyzed in detail by González-Cao et al. [15] from the experimental tests carried out by Kisacik et al. [26]. The wave flume is 22.5 m long by 1.2 m wide and 1 m deep, with an impermeable slope 1:20 preceding an impermeable wall and a overhanging slab. Fig. 3 presents schematics of the test flume. The reference data includes water surface level measurements at 8 wave gauges, and vertical array of 7 high frequency pressure measurements distributed and spaced 0.06 m on the back wall as shown in Fig. 3. Wave conditions tested by Kisacik et al. [26] and simulated in this study were: wave height, $H = 0.065\text{m}$, and wave period, $T = 2.2\text{s}$.

The force on the vertical wall section is obtained by integrating over the pressure sensors:

$$F_h(t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{M-1} [P_{k,i}(t) + P_{k,i+1}(t)] (Z_{i+1} - Z_i) \quad (10)$$

where $P_{k,i}$ and Z_i are, respectively, the dynamic pressure and the location of the i -th sensor on the

Fig. 3. Sketch of the experimental flume with an impermeable wall, pressure sensors and overhanging slab carried out by Kisacik et al. [26].

wall. $M = 7$ is the number of sensors.

The experimental data of Kisacik et al. [26] was chosen to evaluate the effect of using squared or non-squared elements for the mesh construction. To this end, three meshes were evaluated: one mesh of 999 380 non-squared elements, and two meshes with, respectively, 716 078 and 2 227 644 squared elements. The meshes are identified as, respectively: structured-1M, squared-0.7M and squared-2.2M. The latter two were built using *snappyHexMesh* by creating a square grid of uniform element size, cutting out the geometry of the domain and smoothing the boundary faces. Mesh structured-1M was built using *Centaur v.14* by adjusting global blocks to the shape of the fluid domain. The main difference between the structured-1M mesh and the others is that the edges are not aligned with the horizontal direction, which distorts the interface at the beginning of the simulation. The nominal element size is 0.05 m for both structured-1M and squared-0.7M meshes, and 0.03 m for the squared-2.2M mesh. Each case was carried out for 10 impacts (roughly 36 s).

Fig. 4 compares the water interface height calculated with the three meshes against the experimental results analyzed by González-Cao et al. [15]. The wave data correspond to wave gauges WG3 and WG7 (Fig. 3). Overall, the three meshes exhibit a good agreement with the experimental results for both the incident wave form (WG3) and the disturbances caused by the interactions with the wall (WG7). This is verified using the statistical parameters listed in Table 3. The correlation coefficients relative to the experimental data are: 0.934, 0.941 and 0.945 for the structured-1M, squared-0.7M and squared-2.2M meshes, respectively. The *SI* values, respectively: 0.865, 0.876 and 0.885 confirm the model's good performance for capturing the wave surface elevation.

The average force on the wall estimated with Eq. 10 is displayed in Fig. 5. It corresponds to the average of 7 consecutive impacts on the wall as reported by González-Cao et al. [15]. An average force is displayed instead of individual impacts because of the high variability of wave impact data, even under controlled conditions with regular waves. A good agreement is obtained with the three meshes along the ramp up and the secondary bump ($t \geq 0.12$ s). The main difference between the numerical results and the experimental data is the maximum peak force ($t = 0.0$ s), which is overpredicted by the present model for all meshes. The peak force is sensitive to the sampling frequency of the data (the peak value augments with increased sampling frequency), yet the results shown in Fig. 5 are obtained using the same sampling frequency as the experimental source. Moreover, the structured-1M mesh shows oscillations after the initial impact, which are characteristic of highly aerated wave breakers. This behaviour is not supported by the experimental data, which do not exhibit any oscillations (indicating flip through breaker impacts with very little or no entrapped air). The numerical results for both squared-0.7M and squared-2.2M agree better with the experimental data in this regard. Thus, they have better performance statistics as

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Water surface level at (a) WG3 and (b) WG7 (wave gauges in Fig.3). Comparison between the present model results on the three meshes: Structured-1M, Squared-0.7M and Squared-2.2M, and the experimental results analyzed by González-Cao et al. [15] from the experimental test of Kisacik et al. [26].

shown in Table 3. For instance, the correlation coefficients are $R_A = 0.761$, 0.839 and 0.834 for the structured-1M, squared-0.7M and squared-2.2M meshes, respectively. The SI and AI values confirm this trend. The models show a lower accuracy for reproducing the experimental force than the wave surface height, which is expected as the force impacts exhibit a higher variability and involve more complex phenomena. Although mesh squared-2.2M has a slightly better performance, the results are almost identical between all meshes, which indicates that the results are independent of the grid size. Based on these results, the structured meshing approach using snappyHexMesh was adopted for the case described in Section 4.

	E_N	$\sigma_{n,A}$	R_A	AI	SI
Wave gauges (average)					
structured-1M	0.384	1.105	0.934	0.512	0.865
squared-0.7M	0.370	1.114	0.941	0.485	0.876
squared-2.2M	0.353	1.112	0.945	0.460	0.885
Force on the wall					
structured-1M	0.676	0.954	0.761	1.097	0.600
squared-0.7M	0.544	0.849	0.839	0.840	0.696
squared-2.2M	0.553	0.858	0.834	0.857	0.690

Table 3. Comparison metrics for the three meshes versus the experimental results of Kisacik et al. [26] in terms of the wave gauge and force results. Case of wave impacts against an impermeable wall.

Fig. 5. Temporal evolution of the average horizontal force on the wall. Comparison between the present model using three meshes: Structured-1M, Squared-0.7M and Squared-2.2M, and the numerical model and experimental results analyzed by González-Cao et al. [15] from the experimental test of Kisacik et al. [26]

4. Analysis of wave impacts on a coastal protection wall in the Saint-Lawrence Gulf

In this section, the developed numerical model is applied to study the wave impacts over a vertical coastal protection structure along the Saint-Lawrence gulf. The results of wave loads and the corresponding breaker types on the vertical wall are analyzed. Moreover, the cases with overtopping are discussed in this section.

4.1. Numerical domain

The two-dimensional computational domain is presented in Fig. 6. The bottom profile is taken from bathymetry data representative of the coastline along the Gaspé region (Québec, Canada). The maximum depth is 14.42 m at the limit $X = 0$. A vertical impermeable wall of 6.5 m height is located at 159 m from the domain inlet. The still water level (SWL) in front of the wall is $h = 3.8$ m. The domain extends another 86.25 m between the wall and outlet boundary.

Fig. 6. Computational domain of the vertical wall in the Saint-Lawrence gulf with the relevant boundary conditions.

4.2. Wave conditions

Incident wave conditions were collected from the data of a buoy located offshore in the Saint-Lawrence Gulf. The data comprises 56624 instances of deep water waves with wave height $H_o \leq 6.0$ m and wave period $T \leq 10.5$ s, between 2007 and 2019. Wave transformation from the buoy location (deep water), T and H_o , to the wall, T and H_{sI} , was estimated considering processes, such as shoaling and refraction [27]. H_o is the wave height at deep water, T the mean wave period, and H_{sI} the significant wave height.

For each sea state of the data set (H_{sI} and T), the dimensionless force on the wall, $\frac{F}{\rho g H_{sI} h}$, was estimated using the method of Goda [28], which includes Takahashi's correction for impulsive loads. The wave conditions simulated in this work were selected based on the experimental space $[h/L, H_{sI}/L]$, proposed by Díaz-Carrasco et al. [29], and the resulting loads on the wall calculated. Table 4 presents the four inlet conditions chosen for this study, where L and H_{max} are the wavelength and maximum wave height at the front of the structure (estimated values), respectively. Conditions I and II in Table 4 correspond to extreme storm events leading to the highest forces on the wall, whereas cases III and IV represent conditions of lesser magnitude but much more frequent.

Case	T [s]	H_o [m]	L [m]	H_{sI} [m]	H_{max} [m]	$\frac{H_{sI}}{L}$	$\frac{h}{L}$	$\frac{F}{\rho g H_{sI} h}$
I	9.5	5.2	99.70	3.94	7.09	0.0400	0.145	3.11
II	9.8	6.1	103.57	3.47	6.24	0.0334	0.139	2.94
III	10.2	2.5	108.70	1.77	3.19	0.0163	0.133	2.21
IV	5.8	2.6	49.58	1.90	3.42	0.0383	0.291	1.52

Table 4. Wave conditions simulated by the numerical model for studying wave impacts over a vertical wall in the Saint-Lawrence Gulf (Québec, Canada).

4.3. Numerical parameters and conditions

Interactions between the structure and incident regular waves (Table 4) were modelled for 400 s for each case. The waves were generated at the inlet boundary using the *olaFlow* library. This library allows the definition of incoming waves at inlet boundaries (surface height and velocity profile) based on several linear theories, as well as the absorption of outgoing waves at every boundary, thus preventing non-physical reflections. The regular waves in this study were generated using Stokes II theory, following the guidelines in [30]. The bottom boundary is modelled as a non-slip smooth wall. The top boundary is an open atmospheric condition with prescribed total pressure $p_o = 101.325$ kPa. An outlet condition $\left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x_i}\right) = 0$ with wave absorption correction was imposed at the exit.

The structured mesh grid was generated using *snappyHexMesh*. Elements outside the domain are discarded and those along the boundaries are snapped to the geometry. The final mesh contains 1,180,019 rectangular elements. The nominal element size is 0.05 m. This value was imposed from the inlet up to the wall. Element size was reduced by 2 to 4 times in the near bottom region and doubled behind the wall and away from the interest region. Final mesh size was determined following preliminary calculations of case I with different mesh sizes. The finer two meshes in that analysis having nominal sizes of respectively, 0.05 m and 0.07 m, differed by less than 5.6% when comparing the top ten highest forces on the wall, which indicates that the results were independent of the mesh grid at that nominal size.

4.4. Cases I and II - Breaking waves: results and discussion

Fig. 7 depicts a sequence of water dynamic pressure fields close to the wall for Case I during a typical impact in the series. The black arrows show the local velocity. The horizontal black line indicates the SWL. The wave shape in Fig. 7a reveals a plunging breaker type with the wave clashing on the water at about 8 m ahead of the wall. This forms a jet towards the structure followed by a large air pocket. The jet maximum horizontal velocity is about 10 m s^{-1} at this instant. As the water reaches the wall, the jet focuses on a small area just below the SWL (Fig. 7b). Previous observations by [31] found that the maximum pressure point on the wall tends to be located at the SWL during highly aerated breaking wave impacts. In the case of Fig. 7b, it takes place slightly below the SWL. This could happen because the pressure wave reflected from the wall after the impact is constrained against the incoming air pocket, which generates a pressure build-up at this point. The resulting pressure surpasses 208 kPa and generates a large pressure gradient which expels the jet along the wall as shown in Fig. 7c. The jet upwards velocity ranges from 20 to 30 m s^{-1} . The dynamic pressure along the wall decreases to about 100 kPa, but the gradient from the SWL towards top and bottom is maintained. During the analysis, pressure waves from the wall were observed travelling seawards, which generated oscillations on the overall pressure field ahead of the wall. Finally, as the broken wave reaches the wall (Fig. 7d), it pushes the initial jet over the structure, which generates splashing overtopping over the wall.

Plunging breakers are characterized by an initial strong impact occurring in a very short time span. The pressures at the bottom, SWL and top of the structure during the initial peak for Case I (Figs 7b and 7c) are displayed in Figure 8a. Two pressure peaks over 500 kPa are captured at the SWL during the first 0.01 s. These are generated by the arrival of the initial jet and the wave crest respectively. Using pressure-impulse theory, Bredmose et al. [32] showed that pressure waves travel along the wall after the impact, building up pressure at the bottom. This phenomenon would

Fig. 7. Wave impact sequence with dynamic pressure on the vertical wall: (a) to (d) Case I; (e) to (h) Case II.

explain the two pressure spikes observed at the bottom shortly after those at SWL. Despite the noticeable overtopping, the pressure at the top of the wall is very small in comparison. It must be noted that the pressure peaks in Fig. 8a occur in a span of less than 0.2 s. After this initial impact, the pressure along the wall oscillates due to the alternating compression and expansion of the air pockets on the wave front [5].

Fig. 8. Case I - (a) Pressure ($P - Patm$) at bottom corner, SWL and top corner of the wall during one impact in the series. (b) Force on the wall. The black line represents the mean force after 400 s. The dark and light shaded areas cover, respectively, 90% and 99% of the impacts.

For regular waves, it is possible to isolate and group all impacts in each series to obtain an average force on the wall. The impacts were synchronized by aligning the individual maximum peak times at 0 s. The result for Case I is shown in Fig. 8b after 36 peaks. Black line in Fig. 8b represents the average force profile, and dark and light shaded areas represent the 90th and 99th percentiles, respectively. In Case I, the maximum and average forces at the impact peak are 1860 kN m^{-1} and 618 kN m^{-1} , respectively. The important difference between the maximum force attained and the peak average value can be explained by the fact that the waves break before reaching the wall, which adds high variability to the phenomenon, even if the incident conditions are constant. After the initial peak, the force experiences oscillations, which are related to the presence of air. In particular, the successive compression and expansion of the trapped air are typical of highly aerated impacts [31]. These persist for about 2 s. After which, the force decays as the wave recedes from the wall.

For Case II, the incident conditions are fairly similar to Case I. Thus, the same breaker type is expected. As shown in Fig. 7e, the wave breaks almost directly on the structure, curling the crest and the rising wave base onto a single point on the wall. Yet as the wave trough reflects from the structure, the pressure builds up in this region, which deviates the water upwards and towards the incoming wave curl. The horizontal velocity at the wave front in this moment is about 18 m s^{-1} . Once this front reaches the wall, it is split into two parts (Fig. 7f): the top part is deviated upwards along the wall, while the bottom part turns around the air pocket and goes through it and towards the wall. The jet velocity at this instant is up to 40 m s^{-1} upwards and 8 m s^{-1} downwards. The

peak dynamic pressure on the wall (~ 100 kPa) takes place at about 2 m over the SWL, a behaviour already observed by Bullock et al. [31] in large scale impacts with low aeration. It seems as if pressure builds up between the wall and the incoming air pocket. This generates a vertical pressure gradient, which creates the expelled jet and pushes water down along the wall. As the impact progresses (Fig. 7g), the presence of air pockets creates alternating high and low dynamic pressure regions along the wall. These are probably due to the acceleration of the water as it pushes through the bubbles. The resulting pressure field is apparently chaotic and there is no clear pressure gradient direction. Once the bubbles break, the dynamic pressure along the wall becomes more uniform as shown in Fig. 7h. Similar to Case I, inertia driven by extreme velocities propels the jet over the structure, leading to an overtopping event.

The corresponding pressure profiles at the bottom, SWL and top of the structure for Figs. 7e to 7h are displayed in Fig. 9a. In this case, the impact starts with a fast rising peak at the bottom, reaching pressures as high as 950 kPa, which results from the compression of the wave through against the wall as shown in Fig. 7e. This is followed by a pressure peak at the SWL (about 340 kPa), which corresponds to the wave curl impacting the structure. The initial pressure peak at the bottom shows the influence of the relative water depth h/L in front of the structure, which is reduced as the wave trough reaches the structure. This impact also destroys the air pocket, which generates a turbulent air-water mixture at the bottom of the structure. The flow motion generates pressure oscillations in the bottom, whereas the pressure slowly stabilizes at the SWL as the water falls along the wall. The pressure in the top does not show any noticeable rises.

Fig. 9b depicts the resulting average, 90% and 99% forces for Case II (including 35 impacts). The peak force values for the maximum and mean profiles are, respectively, 1999 kN m^{-1} and 1005 kN m^{-1} . These are the highest values captured in this study. Moreover, since the wave plunges right in front of the wall, the air pocket breaks up rapidly after the initial impact, which leads to more uniform flow velocity and pressure distributions along the wall. Moreover, the mean force profile shows no oscillation after the impulsive peak, which is a characteristic of a low aerated wave breaker type [31]. This breaker type often generates peaks of very high force occurring in very short time spans (≤ 200 ms). After this initial peak, there is a secondary bump at $t \sim 2.0$ s owed to the quasi-static force component [33]. This is generated during the wave reflection from the wall, as the water running down the structure is decelerated by the bottom [34].

4.5. Cases III and IV - Non-breaking waves: results and discussion

Cases III and IV are characterized by non-breaking waves on the wall, which lead to lower pressures and thus less force on the structure as there is no impulsive event. Nonetheless, they are also studied because they occur far more frequently than Cases I and II in the buoy data. Figs. 10a to 10d depict the dynamic pressure during a typical impact on the wall for Case III. The black arrows represent the local velocity. The sequence is typical of standing or quasi-static waves reaching the wall. During the wave run-up (Fig. 10b), the maximum upwards velocity is 6.9 m s^{-1} . The dynamic pressure peaks at the SWL and follows the typical profile shown for non-breaking waves in front of vertical impermeable structures [11]. The peak dynamic pressure is ~ 25 kPa both during wave run-up and run-down and always occurs at the SWL. During wave run-up, the pressure gradient peaking at SWL forces the water jet upwards until the water decelerates under gravitational effects (Fig. 10c). Interestingly, there is also a mild pressure peak over the wall top, which is created by the overreaching jet as it falls in an ordained manner. The resulting overtopping is commonly referred to as "green-water" [35]. During the wave run-down (Fig. 10d), the same pressure gradient

Fig. 9. Case II - (a) Pressure ($P - P_{atm}$) at bottom corner, SWL and top corner of the wall during one impact in the series. (b) Force on the wall. The black line represents the mean force after 400 s. The dark and light shaded areas cover, respectively, 90% and 99% of the impacts.

decelerates the falling water. The maximum downwards velocity during the wave run-down period is 3 m s^{-1} .

The resulting pressure profiles at the bottom, SWL and wall top for case III are shown in Fig. 11a. At the SWL, the profile is characterized by a typical double peak shape representing the wave run-up and run-down events. The peak pressures in both cases reach about 27 kPa, with the run-down peak being slightly lower in general. These pressure values are between one and two orders of magnitude lower than in impulsive impacts (Cases I and II). The wave run-up is slightly faster, which is reflected in the shorter first peak. This indicates that at the conditions of Case III, the wave is close to its breaking point [34]. The pressure at the bottom of the wall exhibits a similar profile with the added contribution of the hydrostatic pressure. The pressure at the top of the wall shows a small peak followed by trough as the wave reaches up and begins its descent. The average force profile on the wall after 400 s (33 impacts) is displayed in Fig. 11b. As expected, the lack of an impulsive impact leads to a smoother mean force profile than in Cases I and II. The peak force value reaches 138.6 kPa. After this initial peak, the larger dark shade area indicates some dispersion and thus variability in the second bump for each impact as the waves recede from the structure.

The dynamic pressure contours for an impact in case IV are shown in Figs. 10e to 10h. Wave height in this case is similar to Case III but at half the period, which makes for a steeper wave. However, waves in Case IV are better reflected by the structure, which leads to lower overtopping and lower pressure values on the wall. The maximum dynamic pressure at SWL in this case is 17 kPa both at wave run-up and run-down. The resulting pressure profiles at the wall bottom, SWL and top are shown in Fig. 12a. Similar to Case III, a symmetrical typical double peak shape of standing waves away from breakup is observed [34]. The pressure at the bottom accounts for the static water column. Contrary to Case III, both pressure peaks in this case are very similar both in terms of the peak value as well as the run-up and run-down times. Thus, at the conditions for Case

Fig. 10. Wave impact sequence with dynamic pressure on the vertical wall: (a) to (d) Case III; (e) to (h) Case IV.

Fig. 11. Case III - (a) Pressure ($P - Patm$) at bottom corner, SWL and top corner of the wall during one impact in the series. (b) Force on the wall. The black line represents the mean force after 400 s. The dark and light shaded areas cover, respectively, 90% and 99% of the impacts.

IV, the wave is not close to break on the wall. As expected, the forces on the wall are noticeable lower in this case, as shown in Fig. 12b. The maximum registered force in this case (after 64 impacts) is 109.7 kPa, which is about 20% lower than in Case III. Nonetheless, the average peak is 62 kPa, which is only half the value of the Case III.

Fig. 12. Case IV - (a) Pressure ($P - P_{atm}$) at bottom corner, SWL and top corner of the wall during one impact in the series. (b) Force on the wall. The black line represents the mean force after 400 s. The dark and light shaded areas cover, respectively, 90% and 99% of the impacts.

4.6. Overtopping analysis

The instantaneous overtopping was computed by integrating the water horizontal velocity along a vertical line extending from the wall top to the top numerical domain. Similar to the horizontal force on the wall, the instantaneous overtopping curve for each case was split into individual impacts, which were then grouped to obtain the mean, 90th percentile and 99th percentile curves. These curves are depicted in Fig. 13 for all cases. In Cases I and II (Figs 13a and 13b), the incident conditions represent extreme storm events. These follow the similar trend as the horizontal force, meaning that there is a very rapid run-up towards the peak, followed by a run-down stage. In Case I, the run-down is followed by negative instantaneous overtopping, which represent a short period during which the water on top of the structure reverses towards the sea. In both cases (I and II) the maximum values of overtopping rate are very high (over $12.0 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), but occur during a very short period (under 0.1 s). Moreover, the shaded areas for the top 90th and 99th percentiles suggest great variability and dispersion from the mean profile, which is expected as these cases generate splashing or spray overtopping. The mean peak values for Cases I and II are 8.0 and $8.4 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively.

Cases III and IV (Figs. 13c and 13d) produce green-water type overtopping, wherein the discharge is formed by a uniform water mass running up and over the structure. This produces the profiles of Figs. 13c and 13d, which show a longer run-up time followed by a less prominent peak in both cases. The maximum instantaneous overtopping discharges (at peak) are 3.4 and $0.9 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for Cases III and IV, respectively. The peak values for the mean profiles for these

cases are 2.2 and $0.1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. The difference relative to Cases I and II lies in the fact that these events are less extreme and the incident waves are about 50% smaller.

The instantaneous discharges along with the consolidated results after 400 s of simulation are shown in Table 5. For Cases I and II, the total discharged volume exceeds $200 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$. The excessive discharge in these cases is owed to the fact that the wave height in front of the structure surpasses the wall height. The mean discharges for these cases are 0.587 and $0.674 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$, respectively. These values are close to the maximum mean values predicted using the correlations proposed in EurOtop II [35] for a vertical wall with relative crown heights between 0.69 (Case I) and 0.78 (Case II). In this study, the relative crown height is the wall height over the SWL (2.7 m) divided by the incident wave height, H_{sI} . For Case III, the mean discharge after 400 s is $0.111 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$ and for Case IV it is barely $0.005 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$. As expected, following the impact sequences of Figs. 10a to 10d and 10e to 10h, the overtopping in Case IV is negligible in comparison with Case III despite having similar incident wave heights and breaker types on the wall. The corresponding relative crown heights for these cases are, respectively, 1.53 and 1.42 . For these values, the expected mean discharge values based on EurOtop II [35] would be $0.022 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$ and $0.037 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$ for, respectively, Cases III and IV.

Case	Instantaneous (Fig. 13)		Discharge volume after 400 s	
	Mean [$\text{m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$]	Maximum [$\text{m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$]	Total [$\text{m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$]	Mean [$\text{m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$]
I	8.4	14.8	234.6	0.587
II	8.0	12.0	269.5	0.674
III	2.2	3.4	44.4	0.111
IV	0.1	0.9	2.0	0.005

Table 5. Instantaneous and total discharge over the wall for Cases I through IV.

Fig. 13. Overtopping rate for Cases (a) I, (b) II, (c) III and (d) IV. The black line represents the mean rate after 400 s. The dark and light shaded areas cover, respectively, 90% and 99% of the impacts.

5. Conclusions

In this study, a FANS solver has been developed to model the hydrodynamics of wave interactions with impermeable structures using the *OpenFOAM*[®] framework. The solver uses the adiabatic equation of state, which allows decoupling of the energy equation and greatly simplifies model implementation. After careful validation with experimental data on (1) sloshing tanks and (2) wave impacts against vertical walls, the solver has been applied to study the forces, wave-breaking and overtopping over coastal protection structures along the Saint-Lawrence gulf (Québec, Canada). For that, wave conditions from a buoy were collected and four incident wave scenarios were simulated. Based on the results obtained in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The numerical model is capable of capturing the hydrodynamics of the incident wave impacts against impermeable structures of realistic size, including pressures and velocities around the structure. The detailed profiles of the wave shape during impact and breaking on the structure were also modelled.

- Including air compressibility in the model aids to better represent plunging wave breakers on the wall, since air compressibility largely affects the pressure dynamics of this breaker type.
- Plunging breakers lead to the highest loads on the wall reaching instantaneous force values of 2000 kN m^{-1} . For cases with non-breaking waves, the maximum force captured in the study is one order of magnitude lower: 138.6 kN m^{-1} .
- During plunging breakers, reflections on the bed generate pressure peaks at the wall bottom comparable to those at the SWL. The pressure at the top of the structure is negligible despite the large overtopping volumes.
- During non-breaking wave impacts, the maximum pressure on the wall remains at the SWL. The associated pressure gradient is maintained as the waves reach and recede from the wall.
- Plunging breakers tend to generate spray overtopping, with mean discharge rates of about $0.6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. For the cases with non-breaking waves, the maximum mean discharge rate was $0.111 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and are reduced to $0.005 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ with a 50% reduction in the wave period.

Overall, this study demonstrates the benefit of FANS models with air compressibility for the study of wave dynamics interacting with impermeable structures. Furthermore, real case simulations showed the applicability of this model to study and analyze in detail the processes involved in wave-structure interactions for the adequate design of coastal structures, especially in the context of sea level rising scenarios. Future extensions of this work would be the application in a three dimensional case, the evaluation of different coastal structure designs and typologies, and the use of more advanced turbulence closures such as Large Eddy Simulation.

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